

Enhancing One-Shot CT Image Segmentation with SAM and CLIP Prompt Learning

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Abstract. Recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have witnessed the emergence of foundation models [5, 9] trained on extensive datasets across various domains. Particularly, SAM [5], initially designed for general image segmentation, has gained traction in medical imaging segmentation, with adaptations like SAM-Med2D [2] and MedSAM [7] fine-tuning SAM for medical tasks, while AutoSAM [3] and SAMed [10] modify SAM’s architecture for automated segmentation without prompts. However, automated segmentation without prompts hindered improvement, while fine-tuned SAM lacked automatic prompting. In the medical domain, where acquiring large annotated datasets is challenging, one-shot segmentation methods are crucial, allowing effective segmentation with minimal labeled data. This study explores one-shot medical image segmentation, leveraging SAM and fine-tuned CLIP Surgery, offering automated localization hints. Additionally, we introduce text prompts for SAM, bridging manual prompting and fully automated methods. Our method proposes a one-shot CT image segmentation pipeline integrating CLIP Surgery [6] and SAM, achieving effective segmentation using only annotated CT images from a single patient. We also test the pipeline’s potential with manual prompting. Experimental results show that our method outperforms state-of-the-art methods, particularly for large abdominal organs in one-shot scenarios, addressing the challenges of medical image segmentation effectively.

Keywords: SAM · CLIP Surgery · foundation model · CT segmentation

1 Method

As illustrated in Fig 1, our pipeline, utilizes a frozen SAM and a fine-tuned CLIP Surgery backbone model. It takes a CT image and textual class descriptions as input, producing a similarity map and corresponding points prompt for SAM segmentation. The similarity map is calculated from $S = E_I \times E_T^T$, where E_I and E_T denotes the image embeddings and text embeddings generated by image

Fig. 1. Overall pipeline of our method: We freeze all the parameters in SAM and finetune the parameters in CLIP Surgery. \mathcal{L} is calculated as the DICE loss between the ground truth mask and the similarity map.

Fig. 2. Visualization example of our method, showcasing the segmentation of liver in a single CT slice. **Left to right:** : input CT image, ground truth mask, similarity map, point prompts, predicted mask using generated point prompts, predicted mask with manually added point prompts. Note that red color and blue color denote the generated and manual prompt respectively, with circles representing positive prompts and crosses representing negative prompts.

encoder and text encoder of CLIP Surgery respectively. Positive and negative points prompts are obtained by thresholding the similarity map.

Fine-tuning CLIP Surgery involves adjusting the attention part of the last few layers in both encoders, assisted by gradient low-rank projection techniques, as proposed by GaLore [11], to reduce memory costs.

2 Experiment

We utilized the abdomen subset of the Multi-Atlas Labeling Beyond the Cranial Vault (BTCV) dataset. From a total of 30 annotated samples, one set was selected for the training set, while 12 samples were allocated for the testing set for experiment. The selection of testing set is same as experiment settings in [8].

We compared the DICE scores of seven large abdominal organs with the SOTA methods, as presented in Table 1. Additionally, as illustrated in Fig 2, the

Methods	Memory Cost(GB)↓	mDSC↑	Spleen	Kidney(R)	Kidney(L)	Liver	Stomach	Aorta	Pancreas
MISSFormer [4]	12.14	27.20	17.67	20.32	20.80	69.57	5.83	43.26	12.98
DAE-Former [1]	17.99	31.48	26.90	27.20	28.62	73.96	6.66	44.52	12.48
SAMed [10]	36.76	41.07	56.36	16.00	42.08	78.57	6.44	64.37	23.69
Ours	5.43	42.67	58.14	64.78	50.08	69.13	22.66	21.40	12.53

Table 1. Quantitative one-shot performance and training memory cost comparison between SOTA methods and our method. mDSC denotes the mean DICE score among these organs. The best results on each class are shown in **bold**, while the second best results are underlined.

prompt options retained by our method can enhance segmentation performance through manual prompting.

Our method and SAMed benefit from the strong segmentation knowledge prior of pretrained SAM, demonstrating good performance in one-shot scenarios for most organs. However, our method, with its retained prompting option, has even greater potential, as it can improve segmentation performance with input from manual prompts.

Furthermore, our method significantly reduces training memory costs by only requiring the training of the lightweight CLIP Surgery. In contrast, SAMed needs to fine-tune the entire SAM, resulting in substantial memory costs to store the gradients of the SAM. (Note that the VRAM of a single NVIDIA RTX4090 GPU is only 24GB.)

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